

BLENDING WORD FORMATION PROCESS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation. Blending refers to the linguistic phenomenon of using languages interchangeably within a conversation or even within a single sentence. This phenomenon is not only a linguistic one but also a sociolinguistic and pragmatic one. It allows speakers to express their identity, establish rapport, and enhance familiarity in their interactions.

Key words: blending, telescope words, contamination, acronym, coinage, neologism.

At the present stage of the development of the English language, one of the methods of making a highly effective word is contamination, that is, Blending. Contamination (Blending) is a relatively younger phenomenon in the process of word formation, which became more common in the 20th century, is the combination of two abbreviations as consonants or one abbreviation and one complete base as one lexical unit. Blending is the process of combining two or more languages or linguistic elements within a speech community. The phenomenon of blending, also known as code-mixing or code-switching, occurs when individuals use elements from different languages in their communication.

The resulting new form contains lexical meanings derived from both words. Examples of these include:

Moped (motorcycle + bicycle)

Brunch (breakfast + lunch)

Oxbridge (Oxford + Cambridge)

Motel (motor + hotel)

Smog (smoke + fog)

Workaholic (work + alcoholic)

Adidas (Addi + Dassler)

Eurovision (Europe + television)

Boatel (boat + hotel)

Blizzard (blizzard + disaster)

Word formation in English using the blending method has been analyzed in some studies. They covered the nature, formation, types and other aspects of

Blending. In particular, as Martina Wagner explains word formation processes, including compound word formation, Blending, shortening (acronym), appropriation, neologisms, or (coinage) also draws questions of new words in English into discussion.

Stefan Gris studies the process of Blending word formation in English. He also examines Blending in terms of these questions:

- 1) how to distinguish blending from other word formation processes?
- 2) is it possible to distinguish between the types of blends?
- 3) Why do blends have such a structure?

John Algeo-presents a scheme-and-use-based analysis of lexical blends. It divides blending into three groups: phonemic similarity: a syllable or part of a syllable is distributed between two words. Clipping: Shorten two words and add them. Phonemic similarity and clipping: reduction and addition of two words to a common syllable.

Thomas Pyle and John Algeo studied the fields of linguistics that belong to each era. In their work, researchers have written about word formation through compound words, clipping, Blending methods, as well as their function and forms.

In cognitive linguistics (J.Lakoff, R.Langaker, L.Talmy, U.Cheif, Ch.Fillmore, N.D.Arutyunova, N.N.Boldirev, V.I.Karasik, V.Z.Demyankov, Ye.S.Kubryakova, Yu.N.Karaulov, Yu.S.Stepanov, I.A.Sternin, W.N.Telia, Sh.Safarov, D.S.Khudoyberganova, Sh.Iskandarova, M.Hakimov and hakazo) the penetration of innovative directions in turn makes it possible to consider the processes in the language, including the process of word formation, the “human factor” and “cognitive activity (perception, use, storage and production of information)”. In addition, cognitive reality includes the ability not only to use the lexicon in human activities, but also to form innovations. In this respect, N.N.Boldirev's opinion is important. The process of forming meanings assumes the process of cognitive perception, the perception of a close universe and the acquisition of similar knowledge.

Research suggests that the field of word formation has been much studied structurally-semantically, but has not been sufficiently studied cognitively. The transition of linguistics to a new stage, the focus of which is human cognitive activity, assumes learning in connection with mental aspects, and not at the linguistic level of secondary origin.

Blending is similar to compound words, which is also the derivation of a holistic new word from the addition of two separate independent components. In blending, however, it is formed by adding the first syllable of the first word and it to the last syllable of the second word.

In our opinion, there is a difference between compound words and blends. Compound words consist of an entire single - meaning word (like *dalahovli*, Khan's daughter – ladybird, doorbell – doorbell), while blends consist of word abbreviations and are characterized by the morphological feature of the linkage of components in a compound-cutting and superimposing and linking morphs.

The term Blending refers to a combination of at least one abbreviated, two or more forms. Blending can either simply drop a part of a word or be the result of letters or sounds similar to each other. Blends “mix” the details of the original space, resulting in a qualitative, new conceptual structure. It no longer depends on the original space and has its own capabilities for further development.

According to some opinions, blending is the combination of two or more words to form a new lexeme in the presence of some form of phonemic or graphemic matching.

The term Blending refers to the fact that at least one of the combinations of two or more forms is reduced. Abbreviations can be the result of simply omitting any part of the word or one of the source words. Although sometimes Blending words cannot be analyzed because their basis disappears.

In Uzbek, the term blending means” mixing“,” mixing”, and requires combining parts of two or more words to form a new word. But making a word in a blending method, such as English, is not considered viable in Uzbek. Since English and Uzbek are languages belonging to different families, shortening words to form a new word is rare in Uzbek. In Uzbek, some words lose their initial form and can be compared structurally to blends formed in English as they contract over time, or as syllables and syllables fall.

For example: *Sariq yog‘ – saryog‘*

Nega muncha – namuncha

Qayin ini – qayni

Qayin ona – qaynona

Sakkiz o‘n – sakson

To‘qqiz o‘n - to‘qson

These words are actively used in the Uzbek literary language and are a product of oral speech. In Uzbek, this process is also known as phonetic re-division.

In English, sometimes blends (portmanteau) are called Words. The first blends were accidental and were viewed as occasionalisms.

Lewis Carroll was the creator of the contamination. The term portmanteau was introduced in 1882 by Lewis Carroll. He also used them in literature as a means of artistic representation, naming it “portmanteau” – words. In his book” Through The Looking Glass”, Humpty Dumpty describes the new word as follows:

- Well”slithy

In this, the word “slithy” is formed from the addition of two words meaning “lithe – soft and” “slimy” – slimy. It's like a portmanteau, a word that has a sum of two meanings. Two different words are combining completely unequal meanings and making another word with a new meaning.

L. Some notable examples of Carroll:

Mimsy – (flimsy + miserable)

Chortle (chuckle + snort)

Galumph (gallop + triumph)

Blends are a new word that cannot be analyzed in a stagnant sense, formed by the addition of two motivated words that have become morphemes. It is important to distinguish phonemic compound blends from elliptic forms.

For example, trafficator (traffic + indicator).

This word is not Blending, since there is no new meaning made as a result of the Blending process.

The difference between compounds from blends is that they combine parts of all meaningful words. In particular, the morphological structure is not relevant for blends. Phonological features are much more suitable for blends.

It is worth noting that the absence of a formal maker (formant) in the process of making a word cannot provide a basis for stopping cognitive (mental) imagination from moving to language, there is also such a situation in shortening, conversion.

Economical units, contamination (blends) in English are actively enriching the vocabulary of a number of industries, such as politics, economics, advertising, media. For example, technology-specific contamination (blends):

Computerate (quality) is a term used in the field of computer technology in an advanced sense. It was formed by shortening and adding computer and literate. This was the basis for the emergence of neologism, the educational program computer literacy (computer literacy) in the 70s of the 20th century.

Cybarian is a person who receives, classifies and maintains information from the internet. (cyber+ librarian)

Webinar (web+workshop)

Staycation, stayactioner

Fakeation, fake-ationer (fake+vacation)

Smexting (smoking + texting)

Currently, the new method of Blending in English is to make new lexical units by combining the parts of the last part of the first word that correspond to the first part of the second word.

Examples:

slanguage = slang + language / language defined by excessive use of slang or cant.

celebrity = cell + celebrity / famous criminal.

juliemo = Julie + Elmo / the names of two musician.

alcohol = alcohol + holiday / Holidays that end up being more about parties and getting drunk with or without the meat.

playbore = playboy + bore / a boresome playboy.

anecdote = anecdote + dotage / garrulous old age, anecdotes collective.

backronym = back + acronym / reverse acronym.

cartoon = cartoon + tune / musical cartoon.

Shortened new blends:

There is no uniformity of syllables in abbreviations. Instead, one or more pieces are left to fall. There are different ways to create such blends. Blends are divided according to the number and location of abbreviations. When classified, the usually sequential combinations of source words are understood.

Radar + range = radarange

Such blends are also known as Telescope words.

It has been widely acknowledged that blending – (mixing) in Uzbek takes a leading role in the formation of new conceptual structures, including metaphorical phrases.

Throughout our research, we have witnessed that the formation of new words in the blending method is a feature that is structurally uncharacteristic of the Uzbek language. But we also witnessed the making of certain words in the method of Blending in fiction.

For example, *Shundan keyin baqabullar sayramay qo‘ydi.*(A.Ayub). by shortening the words *baqa+bulbul*, the word *baqabul* is being formed. *So‘tilib ketar* (I.Otamurod) is formed from a mixture of the words *so‘kilmoq-sitilmoq*. Such occasional blends are not used in colloquial speech, they live only as a derivative created by the author in the composition of fiction.

In English, the method of Blending is improving and developing as time goes by, in this way the formation of new words increases, and they are actively used in the process of communication, and even, entering into the composition of the dictionary, become an urgent topic of scientific research. In Uzbek, however, the practice of Blending is considered a historical phenomenon, and it is clear that the formation of a new word in this way is not one of the most productive methods. In the Uzbek language, it is observed to assimilate words from as many other languages as possible, rather than making them short.

For example *univermag, raykom, obkom, ruslit, inyaz, fizmat, oblzdrav, selsovet, Gorono, Oblono, rayono*, etc.

Little has been studied in Uzbek linguistics as a method of Blending word-formation, and only blends relating to specific areas have been considered by

researchers in English. Including A.Kurganov analyzed abbreviations related to the military sphere, while S.Sobirova is focused on blends found in the tourism industry. In our study, we tried to learn how to make a blending word in Uzbek using the example of English. However, in Uzbek linguistics, the field currently considered relevant and currently it began to be widely studied “conceptual integralization”, that is, “blending theory”. One of the first Uzbek leaders was A.Yuldashev spoke about this in his monograph “Linguocognitive study of idiomatic compound words” and analyzed the theory of “conceptual integralization” on the example of compound words in English and Uzbek. Also, B.Djuraev “Терпия ментальных пространств и теория концептуального блендинга” and D.Kisilyov wrote that the “Реализация концептуальной метафоры в прозаическом тексте” was trying to shed light on Blending theory in his work.

The emergence of the term Blending has been argued above to be related to Lewis Carroll's name and his work, “Alice in the world of mirrors”. But some researchers note that the signs of Blending existed in different languages in the ancient centuries.

Another of the problems in this regard is the choice of a term from a synonymic row: Blending, contamination, paronymic attraction, hybridization, telescoping, etc. In the late 20th century, the term telescoping was used in research, while in the 21st century, the term contamination and blending was actively used. This is a consistent classification of terms M.A.Scheifel analyzed in his paper “Понятие блендинга и его отличие от других смежных способов словообразования в лингвистике”. This article will focus on each of the terms and also cover their different aspects.

Thus, as language develops, a lot of new words around us are consciously made through language trends or advertising and unconsciously through language changes over time. The language is always in dynamic change, because now grammar and words are being updated. In a few decades, the language we use can become difficult to understand.

References:

1. Abrosimova L.S. Blending in the aspect of the cognitive-communicative paradigm. // Proceedings of the Saratov University. Philology. Journalism,-2012. - No.1. –pp.18-22.
2. Algeo J. Blends, structural and systemic view. //American Speech 52, Journal of the American Dialect Society, 1977. –P. 56.
3. Bobina L. Cognitive foundations of secondary phenomena in language and speech: monograph. Tambov: M., 2003. -Page 4.
4. Boldyrev N.N. Functional categorization of the English verb. M., 2009. - p. 17.

5. Cannon Garland. Blends in English word formation. Chicago: Chicago Linguistics Society, -R.725-753.
6. Carroll Lewis. Alice's Adventures in the Wonderland and Through the Looking-Glass. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1996. -P. 102.
7. Gries S. Th. Shouldn't It Be Breakfast? A quantitative analysis of blend structure in English Linguistics 42., 2004. -P. 639-640.
8. Ibraeva A.F. Blending as a productive way of word formation in English-language chat communications // Philological sciences. Questions of theory and practice.-2021.- Volume 14. – Issue 9. – pp. 2769-2772.
9. Khudoyberganova D. Anthropocentric study of the text. - T.: Science, 2013.-B. 48.
10. Kremmer Suzanne Schemas and lexical blends. In Motivation in Language: From Case Grammar to Cognitive Linguistics. Amsterdam and Philadelphia: Benjamins, 2003. -P.75.
11. Martina Wagner. Word Formation Processes: How new Words develop in the English language. // LING 301 Lexical Semantics, 2010. -P.1-8.
12. Pyles, Thomas & Algeo, John The Origins and Development of the English Language, 5th ed. Boston: Thomson & Wadsworth, 2005. -P. 224-242.
13. Scheifel M.A. The concept of blending and its difference from other related methods of word formation in linguistics. // Modern problems of linguistics, literary studies, intercultural communication and linguodidactics : materials of the II International Scientific Conference, Belgorod, 2016. - pp. 290-294.
14. Streltsov A.A. Blending: a brief history of misconceptions // Theoretical and applied linguistics. 2021. -No.7. -p. 137.
15. Yule George. The Study of Language. New York: Cambridge University Press, 2006. -P. 58.